

PERCEPTIONS OF MUSLIM COMMUNITY LEADERS OF MALAPATAN SARANGANI PROVINCE ON REPUBLIC ACT 11596

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative phenomenological study explored the Perceptions of Muslim Leaders of Malapatan Sarangani on Republic 11596. Using the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) by Clark and Braun, through an inductive thematic analysis, themes and core ideas from the data gathered were drawn. This study found that in the perceptions of Muslim Leaders Child Marriage causes more disadvantages than benefits and Islam prohibits cohabitation. Muslim Leaders are firm in their stand concerning RA 11596 implementation that they disapprove of Child Marriage and support RA 11596. The Implications of RA 11596 on Religious and Cultural Practices are; that it encourages law adherence over religious practices and it initiates changes in religious and cultural practices. Based on the results, the recommendations are the following: urgent need for all-encompassing training programs that bridge the gap between faith beliefs and the law, helping people see how they can live together peacefully. Prioritizing efforts that raise understanding in different areas and among different racial and ethnic groups as well as develop programs that give girls economic freedom and educational chances as part of measures to fix the underlying social and economic problems that lead to child marriage

Keywords: *child marriage, child cohabitation, the Muslim community, Republic Act 11596*

INTRODUCTION

Child marriage is a violation of human rights, deeply intertwined with cultural practices and identity. For years, it has been scrutinized and debated by children's rights advocates worldwide, transcending boundaries of country and ethnicity. Despite a steady decline over the past decade, child marriage remains prevalent globally, with one in five girls still marrying at a young age. Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) data shows the number of registered marriages by age group and type of ceremony in 2022 shows a total of 26 registered marriages involving a groom or bride under 15 years old and 936 involving a groom or bride aged 15-19, all solemnized under Muslim tradition. In Region XII, there are three registered marriages in which the bride is below 15 years old. In Sarangani, no data has been recorded for children married below 15 years old under Muslim rites. However, in tribal ceremonies in Malapatan, data shows 14 marriages where the bride was between 15-19 years old (PSA, 2023). In December 2021, President Rodrigo Roa Duterte signed Republic Act 11596 or the "Prohibition of Child Marriage Law," that marks an important breakthrough in the fight against child marriage in the Philippines. This law prohibits the marriage, arrangement of marriage including cohabitation of minors or involving minors. Enforcing this statute that align with international treaties present challenges in a diverse country like the Philippines, where multiple legal systems coexist.

The Perceptions Towards Prohibition of Child Marriage Law

Many countries around the world have different standards for the allowable age of marriage, influenced by cultural and religious practices. It is only at the beginning of the 21st century that many nations began enacting laws setting the minimum marriage age at 18 years. However, exemptions still exist in the Philippines for customary practices, notably under PD 1083 (Code of Muslim Personal Law) and the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (IPRA), which recognize the practice of children marrying below the age of 18.

An empirical legal study by Barkah et al. (2023), using a qualitative descriptive approach, demonstrates how an interpretative approach—encouraging a limited and purely textual understanding of Islam's marriage-related teachings—has contributed to the practice of underage marriage. This suggests that perspectives on child marriage are often taught at a doctrinal level.

As the world strives to end child marriage, it is being understood from various perspectives. According to Hamlyn (2022), terms like "perception" are part of an epistemological framework revolving around the concept of knowing. This concept is centered on the idea that knowledge is a part of justified belief or opinion.

Ullah et al. (2021), using a qualitative legal case study, analyzed domestic laws in light of international and Islamic laws regarding the issue of child marriage. One key finding was that, despite international treaties condemning the practice, there is no adequate international legal punishment for child marriage. This study was conducted in Pakistan.

In Bangladesh, Akter et al. (2022) conducted a study to explore why child marriage persists despite the enactment of laws. Using a mixed-method approach to examine legal knowledge, perceptions, and practices surrounding child marriage, they found that adolescent boys and girls aged 10-19 years, as well as their parents, were aware of the law and its penalties. The study identified issues such as dower, poverty, and sexual harassment as contributing factors to the persistence of child marriage. To alter the social norm, the study recommended involving community and policy officials in addressing these issues.

Melnikas et al. (2021) found an important concerns about the legislation and the reality of child marriage practices in their qualitative investigation of marriage withdrawal. They noted that such practices could have unforeseen consequences, forcing parents to conceal their actions, especially in cases where child marriage was a result of pregnancy and family reputation concerns. As poor parenting practices negatively impact the community, it could be unfavorable to the society.

Zaim et al. (2021) in their study reasoned that there is a strong relationship between Islamically-based ethical leadership, competence as a leader, and team performance. Societal development depends how leaders manage their communities since leaders are the front-runners of their communities. Leaders encourages participation of their members and influence them.

These empirical studies are relevant to this research as they explored perceptions of child marriage laws. In particular, it focuses on the leaders' perspectives, which are substantial in understanding social changes and religious beliefs within a Muslim community. As they navigate the challenges posed by changing times and practices, the perceptions of leaders play a vital role in shaping the changes they bring to their communities.

Child Marriage in Muslim Community

Mobolaji et al. (2020) found that, compared to Christians, girls who belonged to other religion such as Muslim and traditionalist, the latter were more likely to marry early. When they reach puberty or start menstruating, Muslim girls are usually married off by their families.

Consequently, girls are disproportionately affected by child marriage, but boys also experience the loss of their youth due to early marriage (Chauhan et al., 2020). When children marry early, their choices become limited, and their opportunities are reduced. Many of them have not fully enjoyed their youth, and when they find someone, they are interested in, it may cause problems between spouses.

In the same lens, Baja and Diaz (2023) in their study highlighted that one of the themes of Tagkaolo couples' insights that surviving early marriage is challenging, and one of their coping mechanisms is parental support.

Furthermore, families suffer when children marry young because they are not emotionally mature and lack independence (Arikarani & Mahersal, 2024). They found that early marriage has numerous effects. One of the most tragic consequences of early marriage is violence against women and girls, particularly in the Muslim community, where males often hold dominant authority.

Based on information gathered from nationally representative demographic and health surveys, one key conclusion regarding intimate partner violence in child marriage is that women who marry after the age of 18 are less likely to experience both physical and emotional abuse compared to women who marry at 14 or younger (Hayes & Protas, 2022).

Islam does not emphasize gender equality but rather biological, sexual, and functional distinctions between men and women. Put simply, Islam promotes gender complementarity over equality, with status and function distinctions related to household, legal, and political leadership (Karim, 2021). This leads to the perception that men are the decision-makers in the household, putting women at a disadvantage in household positions and decision-making.

In this context, women's lack of self-sufficiency is primarily cultural, supported by religious and customary rules (Antonio, 2023). When this mindset is ingrained, it affects their participation in decision-making within the household, family, and other areas of social life. This vulnerability leaves women at the mercy of their husbands in all aspects of life.

A compilation report, taking a learning-centered and participative approach, which emphasizes intersecting topics and conclusions from studies on feminism, finds that due to their lack of experience and power—and the fact that they frequently have no past relationships with their new spouses—child brides are significantly more vulnerable to violence (Ghomeshi et al., 2020). This vulnerability can cause domestic problems, often leading to divorce in Islam.

Unfortunately, early marriage results in problems and separation or divorce. The causes of divorce in early marriages are attributed to two main factors: internal factors (domestic issues and infidelity) and external factors (other environmental circumstances) (Kartini et al., 2022).

Employing the Demographic Health Survey of Indonesia, Widyastari et al. (2020) found that the divorce rate was higher among women with lower educational attainment, rural women, East Javanese women who married early, West Javanese women who delayed marriage, and women with no children. This survey shows that there is a high probability of divorce if the children will marry early. Indonesia is a country which majority of the citizen practices Islam.

Using qualitative and quantitative mixed methods in a study of the effects of early marriage in selected Barangays of Saudi-Ampatuan in the Province of Maguindanao, Philippines, Unos and Calib (2022) found that most respondents agreed that early marriage is practiced in accordance with Shari'ah Law, complying with the essential

requirements of marriage as stipulated in Presidential Decree (PD) 1083. Although the Philippines does not permit divorce, Muslim Filipinos are allowed to divorce if they meet the requirements set forth by the Code of Muslim Personal Law.

These studies, which describe the reasons and results of child marriages in Muslim communities, are related to the current research because they examine how child marriage is perceived, its impact on families, and the disadvantages and benefits it entails for the Muslim community.

Child Cohabitation in Muslim Community

Rule 9, Administrative Order No. 1, Series of 2005, of the Rules and Regulations Governing the Registration of Acts and Events Concerning the Civil Status of Muslim Filipinos emphasizes that marriages must be registered within 30 days, either by the officiating person or by the parties to the marriage, in a Shari'a Circuit Court. If no officiant is present, the marriage should be registered at the Local Civil Registry (Office of Registrar General, 2005)

As stipulated in Article 16, Chapter II (Nikah), Title II of PD 1083, the Code of Muslim Personal Law of the Philippines, the legal age to contract marriage is 15 years old for males and the age of puberty for females. These provisions reinforce the belief that cohabitation is not permitted in the Muslim community. However, for a marriage to be legally recognized, it must be registered, as mentioned earlier.

While the percentage of Filipinos who are formally married has decreased over time, the proportion of people who live together or cohabit has increased. There is a growing acceptance of marriage and cohabitation in the Philippines alongside these trends (Abalos, 2023). However, in the Muslim community, cohabitation or engaging in sexual intercourse before marriage is considered taboo and forbidden. To avoid committing "Zina," couples often marry through religious rites, regardless of whether the marriage is registered.

Islam places particular importance on the family and its members, recognizing that the organization of the family ensures the stability of society at large. Therefore, Islam seeks to protect the family structure from anything that could weaken or damage it (Robaj, 2021). The union of two individuals marks the beginning of this protective framework. Practicing "Zina" (unlawful sexual intercourse) is considered haram (forbidden) by Muslims and can bring misfortune or a curse to the family if they violate the command of Allah.

According to Noreen and Seema (2021), strong marriage systems often result from deep connections to Islam, faith, and reverence for the Prophet Muhammad. Muslims believe that the family is the foundation of society and must be preserved in proper order, beginning with the union of individuals. Whatever their decisions regarding marriage, Muslims always refer to their religious beliefs.

Cohabitation without marriage must be made illegal to uphold moral principles and prevent future transgressions (Zul et al., 2024). In Islam, cohabitation without the sanctity of marriage is considered a mortal sin. Since age is not a barrier in Islam, there should be no couples living together without marriage.

This issue, like child marriage, is directly related to the current study, as there is a thin line between child marriage and cohabitation. When child marriage occurs, cohabitation often follows. It is crucial to understand the significant role that religious beliefs play in shaping these practices.

The Statute Law and the Sharia Law

According to The Family Code of the Philippines (1987), "Marriage is a special contract of permanent union between a man and a woman entered into by law for the establishment of conjugal and family life." It is the foundation of the family, inviolable, and governed by law. The requirements for marriage are outlined in Sections 1 and 2 of the Family Code. The absence of any of the requisite conditions renders the marriage void *ab initio*.

The law stipulates that individuals must meet certain criteria before they can contract a marriage. Chapter II, Article 16 of PD 1083, the Code of Muslim Personal Laws of the Philippines, provides that Filipino Muslims may contract marriage if the Muslim male is at least fifteen years of age, and the Muslim female has reached puberty or is above the age of puberty, and neither party is subject to any impediment under the provisions of this Code. A female is presumed to have attained puberty upon reaching the age of fifteen.

On the other hand, RA 11596 provides that no person below the age of 18 may contract marriage or engage in cohabitation. Further, Article 16 of the Muslim Code specifies that a "wali" marriage of a minor under the prescribed ages is considered a betrothal and may be annulled upon the petition of either party within four years after reaching puberty, provided no voluntary cohabitation has occurred and the "wali" who contracted the marriage was not the bride's father or paternal grandfather.

There is a noted inequality between Muslim law and Philippine law regarding the legal age for marriage (Muslimin & Ummah, 2022). They contend that this disparity arises from the different foundations on which each rule is based. The Muslim law aims to reconcile political conflicts between the Muslim community and the government regarding Islamic rules, while the Family Code follows Western and Catholic legal traditions. Consequently, both systems have distinct religious and cultural considerations.

The spirit of child protection law differs from that of marriage law (Tan et al, 2024). In their study of the relationship between marriage law and child protection law, using a normative juridical approach, they find that marriage legislation allows minors to marry for urgent purposes through judicial dispensation. However, child protection law explicitly prohibits such practices.

As a form of religious manipulation, underage marriages are sometimes justified through a limited interpretation of Islamic marriage teachings. This exegetical approach has contributed to the persistence of child marriage, as it encourages specific interpretations of the Quranic and Hadith texts (Barkah et al., 2023). Using a descriptive qualitative approach, their study explores the connection between child marriage practices and Islamic law's foundational texts.

These studies and legal provisions are relevant to this research as they address the cultural beliefs and customs of Muslims, especially regarding marriage. The shift in cultural practices and their enforcement in contemporary society is a key focus. Today, old practices are often considered violations of children's rights, particularly in the context of child protection, which has become a primary concern of the government.

In line with the newly enacted statutes, the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP), as well as Muslim communities, is mandated to include awareness programs about the impact and effects of child marriage on the overall health and well-being of children. The Muslim community faces challenges in adopting these new policies while maintaining cultural identity, navigating the tension between preserving traditional practices and aligning with contemporary social norms.

Child Marriage in the Context of RA 11596

Signed and passed on December 10, 2021, RA 11596 ultimately addressed the issue of child marriage. It prohibits the act of child marriage and describes penalties for violations. Under this law, the act of enabling or allowing minors to marry or cohabit becomes unlawful. This legislation is not only applicable to the general public but specifically targets Indigenous and Muslim communities, where the practice of child marriage was previously considered legal under customary and Shariah law.

The parents or guardians who give consent, the solemnizing officers, the bride or groom of legal age, and anyone who facilitates or causes the marriage to occur can be charged for violation of RA 11596. The purpose of this law is to protect the rights of children who are deprived of their freedom to choose, particularly those in Indigenous and Muslim communities. This new law strengthens the children's privilege to choose and the right for self-determination in terms of marriage.

To prevent early childhood marriage, local governments play an important role in ensuring the protection and fulfillment of children's rights (Heryani et al., 2020). This law marks the Philippines' bold step in eradicating child marriage within its jurisdiction. It also adopts a whole-society approach, working to protect children from re-victimization and creating supportive societal conditions to discourage the practice of child marriage. RA 11596 also mandated the Department of Welfare and Development as the lead agency to implement the law.

This law and its impact on culture and practices are at the heart of this study. Navigating in these complexities it is important to understand that as community preservation of its

culture is road to self-determination. It presents a challenge for communities like the Muslim community, which strongly ties its practices to religious beliefs. The law serves as a determining factor for where community leaders stand when their deeply held beliefs are challenged by societal reforms.

Society and the Changing of Cultural Practices

Culture benefits people and society in numerous ways. It contributes to communities, localities, education, health, and more, serving as a key determinant of our societal identity as a group. It is what allows communities to adapt to change and evolve, as culture is a product of our environmental and social contexts (Brook et al., 2020). It is the culture that gives a certain group a unique identity. As society change so as the practices of the people in the community.

In certain contexts, tradition holds more value, and cultural endurance is greater, as noted by Giuliano and Nunn (2021). Through various generational tests, they found that populations whose ancestors lived in more fragile, cross-generational contexts tend to value tradition less today and exhibit less cultural resilience. That is why people change when the society introduces new sets of norms.

Societal development, the evolving interpretations of Islamic religious law, and the influence of local and state politics and legal systems all play a role in the continuous transformation of Muslim marriage practices (Jones & Shanneik, 2020). As societal norms shift, it is essential to align religious practices with the broader political and legal systems. In modern Islam, practices considered violations of human rights are being re-evaluated and, in many cases, are no longer followed.

In combating child marriage, fostering substantial youth engagement is crucial. This can be achieved by creating participation opportunities and supporting initiatives financed by a variety of contributors (Tagorda, 2024). He emphasized that youth networks in the Bangsamoro region play an essential role in advocating for change, supporting these efforts with active participation. The evolution of marriage standards in the Muslim community, coupled with youth engagement, is pivotal to the process of cultural transformation.

Although women in Islamic societies enjoy certain religious liberties, their experiences can vary significantly depending on political, sociocultural, and other factors (Ahmed & Ahmed, 2022). Child brides, in particular, will grow to become women who contribute substantially to societal change. Their participation and awareness will have a significant impact on reshaping cultural practices and nation-building.

The relevance of these studies is clear: societal change is inevitable, and communities must evolve to survive. For this evolution to be meaningful, all members of society must be included. To adapt successfully to changes, it is essential to understand how people can preserve their cultural identity and religious practices while navigating modern challenges.

Research Questions

This study explored the perceptions of Muslim community leaders of Malapatan, Sarangani about the implementation of the Act Prohibiting the Practice of Child Marriage and Imposing Penalties for Violations or the RA 11596.

Specifically, the study addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the perceptions of Muslim leaders regarding child marriage and child cohabitation?
2. What is the stand of Muslim leaders on the implementation of Republic Act 11596?
3. What are the implications of implementing Republic Act 11596 on the cultural and religious practices of the Muslim community?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The municipality of Malapatan is located in the southernmost part of the island of Mindanao, Philippines, between latitudes 05°58.22' North and longitudes 125°17.31' East. It is one of the seven municipalities of the Province of Sarangani, Region XII, situated between the Municipality of Alabel, the capital town of Sarangani Province, and the Municipality of Glan.

The name of the municipality is derived from the Blaan language, combining the words "mala" (pepper) and "fatan" (place), as pepper is known to thrive in the area, particularly in the late 15th century. Several sites along Malapatan's shoreline have been designated as marine sanctuaries. The primary sources of income are agriculture and aquaculture. Arabic tombstones and burial sites that the locals claim date back to the 15th century and may contain skeletal remains believed to belong to early European explorers were found at Barangays of Sapu. Malapatan is inhabited by the Tri-people (Christians, Muslims, and Indigenous people) of Sarangani (Sarangani GOVPH, 2023). The Muslim population are more concentrated in the barangays of Sapu Masla, Sapu Padidu, and Tuyan where two Royal House were located.

Special Release on Population, shows that Malapatan has a total population of 80,741 (PSA, 2022). The 2022 Statistics on marriage by municipality reported 14 marriages involving brides aged 15-19 years and two (2) marriages where the groom was between 15-19 years old (PSA, 2023).

Sampling

In selecting the participants, purposive–homogeneous sampling was employed. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in which the researcher selects participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the study. According to Mweshi and Sakyi (2020), it is based on the premise that identifying the most appropriate cases yields the best data, and that study's results are directly influenced by the chosen.

As per Thomas (2022), a sub type of purposive sampling is homogeneous sampling, which is specific to create a sample where all units have similar characteristics and attributes. This approach targeted a selected group of participants with specific predetermined criteria. Participants were selected on the basis of leadership and position of influence within Muslim community. Chiefly, they must serve in the cabinet of the Royal House in charge of marriage affairs. They had to also be religious leaders with experience in Quranic education, and have knowledge of Islamic Sharia law.

For this study, the researcher selected prominent figures within the Muslim community. Preferably they are members of the Sultanate, personnel of the Office of the Municipal Muslim Affairs, religious practitioners, and members of the council of elders within the Royal House. These individuals are entrusted with responsibilities within the Muslim community. They hold significant influence and authority within the Royal House in Malapatan.

Data Collection and Analysis

The approval to conduct the study was submitted to the Office of the Honorable Mayor of Malapatan, Sarangani. Upon receiving approval, the next step was to approach the Office of the Tri-People Council, which includes Municipal Muslim Affairs, to seek permission to conduct a study on the perceptions of Muslim leaders regarding RA 11596 in the municipality. Malapatan does not have a separate office for Muslim Affairs; instead, all matters concerning Muslims are managed by the Office of the Tri-People, which also oversees Indigenous Peoples (IPs), Non-IPs, and Christians. The final approval to proceed with the study was granted by the concerned Royal House. With this, the study was conducted.

An interview guide, duly validated by HTC's Research Panel from the Graduate School, was used to gather insights and perceptions from Muslim leaders regarding the passage of RA 11596. The interviews were recorded for future reference and data analysis. Once the data was collected, it was transcribed and the transcriptions were analyzed to obtain the study's results.

In this study, Thematic Analysis (TA) was used to analyze and interpret the collected data. Themes were identified to highlight common essential ideas within the data. A key feature of TA is its flexibility, allowing for the examination of data across a wide range of experimental concerns (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The themes were employed to interpret concepts with similar inferences, grouping these impressions accordingly.

As a qualitative-phenomenological study, this research encountered complex ideas due to the multidimensional aspects of human experience. Braun and Clarke (2022) emphasized that researchers using reflexive TA should embrace uncertainty, recognizing that meaning is constructed through the interpretation of data rather than being excavated from it. They further noted that decisions on how much data to gather and when to stop collecting data are inherently subjective, and such decisions cannot be fully determined before the analysis.

In this study, Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA), an inductive approach, was employed. In analyzing the data, the concepts were allowed to emerge organically, free from preconceived notions or frameworks. By prioritizing the story told by the data itself, this "bottom-up" methodology allowed for discoveries by remaining open to the narratives that arose directly from the data. From this, themes were identified regarding the perceptions of Muslim leaders in Malapatan, Sarangani Province, on RA 11596.

To organize the data, the Researcher followed the six steps of thematic analysis. First, the Researcher familiarized the data by reading and rereading it multiple times to understand what the data was conveying, while jotting down interesting ideas from the transcription excerpts. Second, codes were generated from the transcribed responses of the participants, doing this manually. Codes were organized according to recurring ideas and patterns. Third, these ideas were used to generate themes, which became the focus of the results presentation. Fourth, the themes were reviewed to ensure that all significant ideas were captured. Fifth, the themes were identified and named based on their patterns, merging themes with similar concepts. Finally, the Researcher produced a narrative report of the findings.

According to Mezmir (2020), carefully reviewing and rereading notes, recording study memoranda, and underlining key sections—using motifs to illustrate specific ideas—are highly beneficial for displaying qualitative data gathered in sociological research. The ideas expressed by the participants in this study are best interpreted through themes, as their perspectives are deeply influenced by their cultural contexts.

The data analysis in this study was reviewed through a peer debriefing process after the thematic analysis, ensuring that all vital information was included. This process was essential to enhance the validity and reliability of the research.

Scope and limitations

This study explored the perceptions of Muslim leaders in Malapatan, Sarangani. It focuses on their insights about child marriage and cohabitation, their stance on the implementation of Republic Act 11596, and the impact this law to religious and cultural practices. It also addressed issues related to child marriage and cohabitation involving members of the Muslim communities in Malapatan, Sarangani Province. To better understand their view on the implementation of the law, it specifically focused on the personal perceptions of the participants. The study also examined the significant changes brought about by RA 11596 during one year transition period. Further, it observed its

impact, and the actions that these leaders may need to undertake to help the community comply with the law.

The participants of this study were selected from the Council of Muslim elders and leaders. Out of these leaders, eight individuals with the most experience in dealing with cases in the Royal House were chosen. Data gathering was conducted at the municipal level, focusing on Barangay Sapu Padidu and Barangay Tuyan, where the Royal Houses are located and where the majority of the residents are Muslims.

The law was enacted on December 20, 2021, and was still in its transition period at the time of the study. Awareness and understanding of its provisions may not have been fully developed; however, addressing the issue was deemed necessary to facilitate concrete action. While the study may have touched on religious beliefs and other values affecting child marriage and cohabitation, it did not delve into other areas of cultural practices. Data was drawn from participants' interviews; therefore, Reflexive Thematic Analysis was used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. It presents the findings on perceptions of Muslim leaders on RA 11596, it follows the orders of the research question. It started with the perceptions of Muslim leaders regarding child marriage and child cohabitation; the stance of Muslim leaders on the implementation of Republic Act 11596; and the implications of implementing Republic Act 11596 for the religious and cultural practices of the Muslim community.

Table 1

Perceptions of Muslim Leaders on Child Marriage and Child Cohabitation

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Child Marriage has More Disadvantages than Benefits	Jealousy of Spouse	Typical
	Presence of Domestic Violence	Typical
	Separation of Couple	Typical
	Unreadiness for Responsibilities	General
		General

Islam Prohibits Cohabitation	Living Together Outside Marriage is a Mortal Sin
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Table 1 presents the perceptions of Muslim leaders regarding child marriage and cohabitation. In this particular issue, two themes: Child Marriage has more disadvantages than benefits and Islam prohibits cohabitation, and five core ideas were identified.

Table 2

Stand of Muslim Leaders Concerning RA 11596 Implementation

Major Theme	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Disapproves Child Marriage and Supports RA 11596	Muslim leaders trust RA 11596 as a government program	Typical
	RA 11596 upholds the rights and well-being of children	General

Table 2 shows the stand of Muslim leaders of Malapatan concerning RA 11596. It showed their support and non-support when it comes to the implementation of the said law.

Table 3

Implications of the Implementation of RA 11596 on Religious and Cultural Practices

Major Themes	Core Ideas	Frequency of Responses
Encourages Law Adherence over Religious Practices	Accountability of Violators of RA 11596	General
	RA 11596 Reinforces Children's Social Protection and Responsibility	General
Initiates Changes in Cultural and Religious Practices	RA 11596 Fosters New standard of practice for Muslim Community and Family Values	Typical

Table 3 presents the implications of the Prohibition of Child Marriage Law on religious and cultural practices, represented through two key themes. First, the law is expected to encourage adherence to legal standards over cultural, religious, or traditional practices. Second, it is anticipated to initiate changes within these cultural and religious practices.

DISCUSSION

Perceptions of Muslim Leaders Regarding Child Marriage and Child Cohabitation

Child marriage and cohabitation are complex issues that involve religion, culture, and law. This study was conducted following the transition period between December 2021 and December 2022 specified by RA 11596, which required the National Commission for Indigenous Peoples (NCIP) and the National Commission on Muslim Filipinos (NCMF) to conduct information dissemination regarding the prohibition of child marriage.

Muslim leaders' knowledge of the law is crucial, as it forms the basis for understanding their perceptions of issues that may affect the implementation of the Prohibition of Child Marriage Law. Child marriage is deeply embedded in certain Muslim religious and cultural practices and it is been practiced ever since. The changes brought by this law will determine their acceptance and their discernments about its execution.

Child Marriage Has More Disadvantages Than Benefits

This major theme addresses the disadvantages that child marriage may bring to the community. It presents five core ideas: jealousy of spouses, presence of domestic violence, separation couples, and the unreadiness for responsibilities. These themes and core ideas are derived from the experiences and problems encountered by the Muslim leaders of Malapatan, Sarangani Province, which were discussed within the Royal House.

Jealousy of Spouse. It is a common problem among newly married couples. Leaders spoke not only from observation but also from firsthand experience. Participants discussed the challenges of marrying at an early age. While Islam permits a man to have more than one wife, provided he complies with the Quran and the requirements of PD 1083 (Code of Muslim Personal Laws) for second and successive marriages, this practice often becomes problematic when the man engages in relationships outside of his marriage. Such actions lead to jealousy.

The participants cited that the main problem was that jealousy started from the boy's act because they have no self-control and the thought of having the privilege to be able marry more than one, do not help the situation. It would result to problem.

Lack of self-control due to age, when individuals are supposed to be enjoying their youth, can trigger jealousy from their partners. In Islam, men often hold the belief that they are allowed to be with other women besides their wife, giving them the freedom to pursue other romantic interests. This notion highlights the chaotic lives of couples who marry at an early age, especially during the adjustment period when they are navigating the complexities of married life.

This finding strongly correlates with a qualitative study by Chauhan et al. (2020), which suggests that early marriage deprives boys of their youth, while girls are disproportionately affected by child marriage. When children marry young, their options are limited. Robbing children of their childhood can have significant consequences. As their choices become restricted, they may neglect their spouses, with girls particularly bearing the emotional strain, especially in cases of infidelity. In the Muslim community, where men are allowed to have more than one spouse, this practice may foster jealousy, as there is no assurance that a woman will be the only one

Presence of Domestic Violence is another consequence of early marriage. The leaders noted that violence cannot be overlooked when a child marries early. Republic Act 9262 defines domestic violence as not only physical but also psychological, sexual, and economic violence. Leaders reported encountering cases lodged in the Royal House where physical abuse had occurred. In addition to physical abuse, economic and psychological abuse were also prevalent. These forms of abuse are considered domestic violence and have a significant impact on children subjected to early marriage. cited that the immaturity of the parties involved is a key factor contributing to the issue. The family, the wife, and the children may face neglect. Children are particularly vulnerable, as they often bear the brunt of the parents' unpreparedness. Participants also identified this as one of the primary reasons for the large number of neglected children. In such situations, if the parents intervene, the issue often escalates beyond the couple, affecting both families.

Women's lack of autonomy is primarily cultural, supported by religious and customary rules (Antonio, 2023). This is a driving factor behind domestic violence and exacerbates the situation of child brides. In a patriarchal community like that of Muslims, when a Muslim female marries, her economic, human, and reproductive rights are often neglected. Decisions are typically made by male members of the community, and the woman comes under the authority of her husband.

Hayes and Protas (2022) findings from analysis of nationally representative Demographic and Health Surveys concluded that women who married after the age of 18 were less likely to experience physical and emotional abuse compared to those who married at 14 or younger. Muslim leaders believed that because children are assigned responsibilities for which they are unprepared, domestic violence resulting from child marriage is an issue that cannot be ignored. Child brides, due to their lack of experience and power, as well as their lack of prior relationships with their spouses, are significantly more vulnerable to violence (Ghomeshi et al., 2020).

Separation of Couple. Due to their immaturity, couples often act according to their beliefs, which may ultimately lead to divorce for Muslims. Under the Family Code of the Philippines, divorce is not permitted in civil unions or Christian marriages. However, under the Code of Muslim Personal Law (PD 1083, Section 45, Chapter 3, Title II), divorce is allowed in Muslim marriages.

A study by Unos and Calib (2022) used both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the effects of early marriage in selected barangays of Saudi-Ampatuan, Maguindanao. The study found that the majority of respondents practiced early marriage in accordance with Shari'ah law and Presidential Decree 1083, fulfilling the required requisites for marriage.

Seeking a divorce in Islam is a relatively simple process compared to annulment in civil law, which is time-consuming and involves a lengthy procedure. If one party insists on separating, leaders in the Royal House have no choice but to respect the decision made by both parties. Widyastari et al. (2020) study found that the proportion of divorces was higher among women with lower educational attainment, rural women, East Javanese women who married early, West Javanese women who delayed marriage, and women with no children. In the Philippines, although divorce is not yet legal, Filipino Muslims can seek divorce through the Sharia Court.

Unreadiness for Responsibilities sometimes compels the parents to assume the responsibilities of the young married couple, particularly when both are still dependent on them. Participants noted that when a couple marries but is unprepared for the responsibilities it entails, they often become a burden to their parents.

Contrary to the common belief that child marriage will alleviate the economic burden, Participants 1 and 2 who handle community issues, emphasized that it actually exacerbates the financial strain on parents as the children are not yet prepared to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage. The issues typically brought before the Royal House revealed that economic struggles are a recurring concern when child marriage is involved, often leading parents to intervene.

Participant 5 stated these actions will always boomerang to the parents. Children have often no consciousness of the gravity of the obligation which make them irresponsible of their duty as married couple. Unquestionably participants believe that there is no good result of being married early.

P6 stresses that if the children have finished their study before marrying, chances are, they will be able to stand on their own. The main issue here is that if children marry early, they have no means for livelihood. In Islam marrying more than one is not uncommon however the fall back is that the bigger family the more responsibilities to give the children a better future.

These statements demonstrate that the consequences of child marriage inevitably fall back on the parents. Based on the challenges participants have encountered, they assert

that there are no positive outcomes from child marriage, as the responsibility consistently returns to the parents. This is largely because the children involved are not equipped to provide for themselves.

A qualitative study by Arikani and Mahersal (2024) on the phenomenon of early childhood marriage finds that families suffer when children marry young because they are not emotionally mature enough and lack independence. This finding aligns with the experiences shared by the leaders, who observed that such cases often arise in the grievance committee of the Royal House. The impact on families and relationships is significant, as children are not mature enough to manage the responsibilities and complexities of marriage.

Early marriage does not only affect one community, but, as shown by the insights of these leaders, the disadvantages of early marriage are universally felt, regardless of ethnicity. Baja and Diaz (2023) investigated the impacts of early child marriage using phenomenological inquiry and purposive sampling. Their study revealed that one of the common themes among Tagkaolo couples was that surviving an early marriage is difficult, with parental support serving as a key coping mechanism. This finding aligns with the situation described here, where parents remain deeply involved in their children's lives, particularly in ensuring their survival after early marriages. Marrying off their children does not alleviate the burden but instead, intensifies it.

Islam Prohibits Cohabitation

This theme addresses the belief that cohabitation without marriage, or living together without a formal union, is not practiced in the Muslim community. The only core idea under this theme is that such cohabitation is considered a mortal sin.

Living Together Outside Marriage is a Mortal Sin. In Muslim society, marriage holds great significance, regardless of whether it occurs early or later in life. The views held by Muslims on this matter are rooted in their religious context. P1, P2, P3, when asked about living together without the sanctity of marriage which is a very common practice today, they fervently answered that it is forbidden because the religion thought so. The religious context of these statements focused on the avoidance of committing sin due to temptation. The purpose of conducting the wedding ceremony is to make the cohabitation or sexual relations morally right in the eyes of God and the community. Having sexual relations before marriage is not a simple fornication but considered a grave sin or "Zina".

Participants' statement provides a comprehensive view of how participants feel about child marriage and cohabitation. By examining the significance of marriage in Muslim culture and the specific age limits established by religious traditions, it becomes clear how these religious and cultural beliefs shape the leaders' perspectives on these pressing social issues. When considering RA 11596, a deeper understanding is required to address religious practices in a way that respects them without being discriminatory. Participants stated that, unlike in Non-Muslims and Indigenous "Lumads" communities, which are generally more tolerant of cohabitation without marriage, Muslims are forbidden

from living together unless they are married under Muslim rites. This statement highlights the differing perspectives of various groups on the concept of cohabitation.

Leaders discussed the sacredness of marriage, emphasizing its divine nature and its importance in fulfilling both spiritual and cultural obligations. All Muslim leaders agreed on the significance of marriage as a means of protecting individuals from actions forbidden in the Quran. As Noreen and Seema (2021) suggested strong marriage systems are often the result of deep ties to Islam, reverence for the Prophet Muhammad and faith in religious teachings. Understanding the importance of marriage to Muslims helps contextualize their views on child marriage and cohabitation within the framework of Islamic customs. Leaders emphasize the moral obligation of a Muslim when it came to the idea of marriage.

Cohabitation must be made illegal to uphold moral principles and deter future crimes (Zul et al., 2024). Based on the statements of Muslim leaders, there is a clear connection between religious faith and behavior in society. Participants strongly believed and emphasized that living together without marriage is considered "Zina" (fornication or adultery) in Islam.

Stand of Muslim Leaders Concerning RA 11596 Implementation

This study aims to examine if RA 11596 has caused Muslim leaders to change their views towards child marriage, and how these changes influence the communities they lead. This is in an effort to gain insight on how the RA 11596 has impacted the outlook of Muslim leaders on the subject. It will further help us appreciate the trifocal dimension of the problem of child marriage in terms of law, religion and culture.

Muslim Leaders' Disapproved Child Marriage and Supports for RA 11596

This key theme shows that Muslim leaders are actively against the practice of child marriage within their communities. One significant legislation that aims to address this is Republic Act No. 11596 or RA 11596 which sets forth clear guidelines for the minimum age of marriage. For this, they open up to resisting child marriage as an established norm; they don't hide that they are reconciling with the traditional system of being married young for religious, moral and culture-based logics. By examining both the negative and positive aspects of disapproval and support, the theme highlights the complexity of the issues surrounding child marriage and how Muslim leaders are advocating for legal solutions.

Muslim leaders Express Trust in RA 11596 as a Government Program. Aimed at addressing the issue of child marriage, in the first core idea, what drives their support for the legislation is their confidence in the government's commitment to protecting the rights of children. They view the passing of this law as a positive step toward upholding the well-being of children by setting clear legal boundaries around the minimum age of marriage. P1's statement reflects trust in the government and its programs, supported by P7's assertion that "we have to follow the law because it is not wrong." leader's influence is

crucial within the community. Islam emphasizes the importance of family structure as the foundation of a well-organized society. According to Robaj (2021), Islam takes specific care to protect the family and prevent anything that could undermine its stability. Leaders, as caretakers of the community, serve as role models who must balance their religious obligations with the welfare of the community, understanding that their guidance can promote the well-being of society as a whole.

RA 11596 Upholds the Rights and Well-being of Children. Since the law itself is sound, all participants who signed the comments expressed strong, unanimous support for RA 11596, which prohibits child marriage. The fundamental belief driving this support is that, based on their own views and personal experiences, child marriage has no positive impact on the welfare of children. They believe that RA 11596 offers an opportunity to uphold the welfare of children. Other participants justified the reason of their support to the law because it will help the children to have a better chance for their future.

Rallying around recognition and upholding youths' rights and welfare is key to combating child marriage, a major concern at the heart of the question. Children take on an active significant role in this collective action. According to Tagorda (2024), creating venues for engagement and engaging several donors to support such measures aim at a strong youth conclusion in their effort to accomplish positive change.

Heryani et al. (2021), explored the role of local governments in combating child marriage. They have found that it is critical that we effectively end child marriage if we are to protect and realize the rights of children. This discovery is relevant to our present circumstances. Frontline support is crucial in RA 11596. The same for fulfilling its mission of protecting the rights of children.

The Prohibition of Child Marriage Law (Republic Act 11596) recognizes the vital role of youth in the national development. It promotes and protects their social, moral, intellectual and physical well-being. For this program to be successful, the state must rid itself of any practices and socio-cultural laws and codes that perpetrate prejudice, violence and exploitation of children especially child marriage.

Implications of the Implementation of RA 11596 on Religious and Cultural Practices

The law's implications on religious and cultural practices examines how this interacts with deeply rooted cultural traditions in the Philippines. The aim of the study is to shed light on the complex relationship between legal and traditional practices. It provides a full understanding of the impact and significance of RA 11596 on Filipino society.

Encourages Law Adherence Over Religious Practices

The complex web of Filipino cultural traditions regarding child marriage is examined, along with the extent to which these traditions are followed. By examining how deeply these practices are ingrained in people's minds, this theme aims to provide a more complete picture of the challenges and complexities in reconciling religious and cultural norms with legal requirements, especially regarding Republic Act No. 11596.

Accountability of Violators of RA 11596. The accountability for actions under RA 11596 is a key factor in ensuring adherence to the law. This core idea emphasizes the importance of responsibility for one's actions. People are more conscious of their behavior when it is paired with accountability. The law holds violators accountable for their actions. Participants stressed that the government strongly advocate against child marriage and it is serious in implementing the law to protect its assets. It will certainly seek those who oppose it.

Participants highlighted in their statement that awareness of the accountability associated with actions prohibited by law serves as a deterrent for potential lawbreakers. Participants also recognize that, as leaders, they are not exempt from accountability if they violate the law.

This is evident in Section 5 of RA 11596, which clearly outlines unlawful acts, including the solemnization of marriages, as well as the involvement of parents, facilitators, and individuals who cohabit with a child outside of wedlock. Those found guilty of these acts will face penalties, including imprisonment. The most severe consequence is that parents may be deprived of their parental authority over their children. RA 11596 does not grant exemptions for the application of customary law, including in the context of IPRA and the Muslim Code of Personal Law.

RA 11596 Reinforces Children Social Protection and Responsibility, ensuring that those most affected by child marriage will have better opportunities in the future. This core idea anticipates positive changes, including enhanced educational opportunities, improved gender equality, and broader societal benefits that will result from the effective implementation of RA 11596. Leaders' belief that RA 11596 may strengthen social protection by reducing children's vulnerability to unfavorable circumstances associated with early marriage. By fostering the right mindset and compelling parents to take responsibility for their children's education and well-being, the opportunities for a better future and improved economic status. Additionally, the law provides protection for children who are victims of sexual abuse, where the perpetrator may use the marriage as an excuse to justify their actions or even engage in marital rape.

Using a statutory, conceptual, and legal approach, Heryani et al. (2021) found that local governments play a crucial role in defending and upholding children's rights and in preventing early childhood marriages. Children are particularly vulnerable to such mistreatment and cannot defend themselves. It is the responsibility of community leaders to take action to shield them from abuse and exploitation. The prohibition of child marriage, supported by these leaders, will undoubtedly benefit children.

Initiate Changes in Cultural and Religious Practices

This theme explores the perception of Muslim leaders regarding how RA 11596 initiates change in cultural and religious practices. It is based on two core ideas: RA 11596 fosters new standard of practice for Muslim community and family values, and leaders became

advocates against customary practice of child marriage. It may be subtle but it is crucial. Everything that goes through a change always started in the initiation stage.

RA 11596 Fosters New Standard of Practice for Muslim Community and Family Values. Participants highlighted how education through awareness can change people's mindsets. This awareness will impact cultural and religious practices because both leaders and community members, in an effort to avoid legal repercussions, will make changes to their customary religious practices regarding child marriage. Their statement provides a personal perspective and emphasizes the importance of family in decision-making. Furthermore, one must be conscious of their behavior to adapt to social change. This adjustment, in turn, influences their values.

This core idea aligns with Jones and Shanneik's (2020) study, which discusses how societal development, changing interpretations of Islamic religious law, and the impact of local and state politics and legal systems contribute to the evolving standards of Muslim marriage. As leaders navigate these changes, which are timely and relevant in the current context, they also influence community values. This highlights the importance of understanding how Republic Act 11596 impacts the values within the Muslim community.

Although women in Islamic societies enjoy certain religious liberties, their experiences can vary significantly depending on political, sociocultural, and other factors (Ahmed & Ahmed, 2022). As the most vulnerable members of society the experiences and practices of these girl children who will eventually become women determines their contribution in nation building. By adhering the law, this will empower children to have a part of decision making which differ to the common practice in a patriarchal society.

Children must be given opportunities for participation, as youth engagement is crucial in combating child marriage (Tagorda, 2024). In modern society, addressing issues related to family values requires children's active participation. Providing them with better choices and encouraging them to exercise their rights ensures a brighter future. This is essential for fostering positive family and community values.

Leaders Became Advocates Against Customary Practice of Child Marriage. Since time immemorial, religious leaders has strong influence when it comes to religious and cultural practices. The long-standing religious practice was the result how the community leaders like the Muslim upholds their practices. Section 10 of RA 11596 mandates the National Commission for Muslim Filipinos to conduct an awareness campaign for its members, in collaboration with other implementing agencies.

When leaders were asked about their plans and how they would influence their members to adhere to the law, given its positive impact on their community, participants consider in initiating change in a community practice in how well aware the recipient and their capacity to be involve to make gradual or even drastic change. Because it concerns their community, participants recognized the importance of the awareness and involvement especially the other leaders of the community. Participants consider that being the advocate will be a first step for positive community development.

Zaim et al. (2021) asserted that there is a strong connection between Islamically-based ethical leadership, competence as a leader, and team performance. Participants' responses shows that they are even willing to extend beyond the four walls of their office just to help their community understand that change is really coming and they are part of it. Muslim leaders in Malapatan are now compelled by law and social responsibility to contribute to the sustainable development of the Muslim community through active engagement in this advocacy.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, it is found that the Muslim leaders viewed that the child marriage based on their personal experience and observation that is has more disadvantages than benefits to the children. Meanwhile they believed that based on religious context, there is no considered child cohabitation in Muslim community since the allowable age to marry as stipulated in Code of Muslim Personal laws is when children reach the aged of puberty. For them it is deemed morally right because there is no cohabitation allowed without undergone wedding ceremony through Muslim rites. Thus, the Muslim leaders stand with the regards to its implementation is that, they personally disapproved child marriage and support the implementation of RA 11596 because they trust this as a program of government that upholds the rights and well being of the children.

Consequently, the implication RA 11596 or the "Prohibition of Child Marriage Law" initiates changes in their cultural and religious practices because its fosters new standard of practice Muslim community and family values like prohibiting their children to marry early although it is allowed by religious beliefs and it give children the freedom to choose whom to marry unlike the traditional practice wherein the parents are one who arranges the marriage of their children. It also encourages or make the leaders became advocates against customary practice of child marriage.

Leaders acknowledged the detriments practices of child marriage to both family and children. When it came to the implementation of RA 11596 and its impact on cultural and religious customary practices, the leaders are ready to make adjustments as long as it would be for the common good and for the welfare of children. It must be hard for them to deviate from their customary practice while maintaining their community's' culture both from a perspective of religious identity and culture. Leaders are influencers of their constituents. As society change so as the practices. Compromise is necessary for the survival of the community. It is not about defying the religious belief but upholding what should be done for the good of society especially in protecting the rights of children in the Muslim community.

Recommendations

There are some recommendations to navigate the complex challenges that arise when Muslim organizations to comply with Republic Act 11596 and address child marriage and cohabitation;

First, there is a pressing need to provide comprehensive training programs to connect the faith beliefs people hold to the law that can help them understand how to harmonize these two worlds peacefully. These programs must involve religious leaders, parents and community members as well to work together to change attitudes and dismantle deeply ingrained cultural practices that sustain child marriage.

Second, lawmakers need to prioritize funding toward efforts that raise awareness in other regions and among different racial and ethnic groups, as Muslim communities are not monolithic. That includes pointing out the merits of Republic Act 11596 and correcting misconceptions, understanding the law and accept it.

Third, it must be combined with broader measures targeting the root social and economic drivers of child marriage, including programs that empower girls, enabling them to assert economic independence and access education. These issues are complex and so they require a multifaceted approach, entailing education, awareness, as well as economic and legal empowerment.

Further research and continued monitoring are needed to measure the effectiveness of Republic Act 11596 and its areas for improvement. By coming together like this, society can ensure that children`s rights, and well-being are a priority which can ultimately lead to the end of children being married off to adults, especially in Muslim communities. The present study has contributed novel insights to matters not previously encountered and highlighted areas that require consideration.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The Researcher ensured that all ethical considerations were followed as mandated by the Holy Trinity College because it helped to avoid engaging in practice which implicitly or explicit abuse those whom she seeks to do research with.

To ensure that the informed consent was obtained from the participants prior to their involvement, they were provided with comprehensive information about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and the collection of data. It was provided with the interview guide and outlined the participants` right to be informed about all aspects of the study. The informed consent form states the participants` right to withdraw from participation at any time without reason or penalty and the right to access their data. Participants, additionally, had the opportunity to voice any questions or concerns about the data collection process. Their well-being is safeguarded throughout the conduct of the study. Participants had signed up to be part of the study and all the data they shared was kept confidential. The names of participants have been anonymized with codes. In this study they are referred to as P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, P6, P7 and P8. No part of such information provided by participants was shared with third parties without their explicit permission, except as where such sharing was consistent with the initial disclosure. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study. There was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and all results were used purely for research.

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